

ADAPTOGENS : STRESS-MODULATING PLANTS IN MODERN PHARMACY

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Abstract :

Adaptogens are plant remedies that promote homeostasis and increase non-specific stress resistance, a physiological condition linked to neuroendocrine-immune system issues. These herbs, which contain pharmacologically active phytonutrients like flavonoids, phytosterol, alkaloids, vitamins, lignanes, ecdysones, and triterpenoids, are used in traditional medical systems and mainstream medicine to treat stress-induced and aging-related disorders. Adaptogens are rich in a range of biologically active compounds, including flavonoids, phytosterols, alkaloids, vitamins, lignans, ecdysones, and triterpenoids, all of which are significant in medicine. These substances are widely used to improve physical stamina and manage stress. Adaptogens and immunomodulators like *Rhodiola rosea*, *Withania somnifera*, *Tinospora cordifolia*, *Bacopa monnieri*, *Emblica officinalis*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Asparagus racemosus*, *Ocimum sanctum*, and *Panax notoginseng* are known for their strong antioxidant and anti-cancer properties, owing to the diverse biologically active compounds they contain. They control important stress mediators and physiological markers, such as glucose, cortisol, nitric oxide (NO), cholesterol, and triglycerides. Scientific evidence supports the use of active secondary metabolites present in adaptogens.

Keywords : Adaptogens, HPA axis, stress, rhodiola, withania, ginseng, traditional medicine system.

1.Introduction:

Phytoadaptogens (often referred to as ‘adaptogens’) are a class of herbal medicines commonly used by herbalists – in multiple traditional medical systems – to assist in reducing the negative impact that chronic stress has on health[1]. Adaptogens are synthetic compounds (bromantane, levamisole, aphobazole, bemethyl, etc.) or plant extracts that have the ability to enhance the

body's stability against physical loads without increasing oxygen consumption[2].The term adaptogen refers to “metabolic regulators which increase the ability of an organism to adapt to environmental stressors and prevent damage to the organism by such stressors”. This definition was suggested and agreed upon at an International Conference on Adaptogens in Gothenburg, Sweden in 1996[3]. The definition of “adaptogen” was first introduced in the mid-twentieth century by the Soviet toxicologist Lazarev[4]. During World War II, many stimulants were administered to pilots and submarine crew members to increase their mental and physical performance. Early research on *Schisandrachinensis*' stimulating and tonic effects was published in Soviet Union military journals during WWII. During the period 1950-60, the idea of using herbal medicinal plants to increase stamina and survival in harmful environments was developed, and the toxicologist Lazarev introduced a new concept of "adaptogens" to describe compounds which could increase "the state of non-specific resistance" in stress[5]. Adaptogens might normalize chronically elevated cortisol/corticosterone levels, presumably through their interaction with the glucocorticoid receptors, helping to restore the balance of the HPA-axis[6]. Adaptogens have recently been defined as natural metabolic regulators that increase the ability of the organism to adapt to environmental factors and to avoid damage from such factors[7]. Almost every plant preparation that has been shown to have some beneficial effects can be classified as an adaptogen.. Because the premise of adaptogenic action requires further explanation, this term is not accepted in clinical or pharmacological terminology in the European Union and has been deemed inappropriate for marketing authorization[8]. The usage of adaptogens has grown in popularity because they are available without a prescription. For example, according to the National Institutes of Health Office of Dietary Supplements, there are currently more than 1,300 products containing *Withaniasomnifera* in the United States markets alone and by 2019, preparations derived from this plant had become the fifth most popular dietary supplement[8]. The beneficial stress-protective effect of adaptogens is related to homeostasis regulation via several mechanisms of action associated with the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, as well as the control of key stress mediators and biochemical markers such as nitric oxide (NO), cortisol, cholesterol, triglycerides, glucose, and so on[9]. Stress is a substantial part of life, however Stress is “the nonspecific response of the body to any demand”, as defined by Hans Selye, the founder of stress theory [10]. He referred to this theory as the “general adaptation syndrome,”¹ a stress model based on physiology and psychobiology. Stress

can range from short-term daily hassles to long-term unsettling conditions that can compromise an individual's health and well-being[11]. chronic stress or ongoing exposure to stressors can disrupt the balance of the HPA axis, resulting in a prolonged elevation of cortisol levels[12]. Stress may be both positive and pro-adaptive and is a part of everyone's life. Long-term exposure to stressful events or surroundings is detrimental to mental health and stands as a risk factor for numerous neuropsychiatric illnesses such as depression, mood swings, and anxiety. [13]. Stress can become chronic and function as a trigger for chronic degenerative diseases (such as type 2 diabetes, hypertension, hormonal imbalances, and obesity) if the human adaptive response fails to address it[14]. In 1948, extensive research conducted in the former Soviet Union demonstrated that adaptogens enhance physical and mental performance during periods of stress. These substances proved beneficial in treating conditions like asthenodepressive syndrome and neurasthenia, which are marked by symptoms such as fatigue, weakness, irritability, headaches, general discomfort, insomnia, lack of appetite, cognitive and memory issues, as well as stress, depression, and anxiety. [15]. Stress management calls for emotional and physical adjustments to regulate and lessen the tension brought on by stressful circumstances. Its pharmacological treatment includes antidepressants or tranquilizers (*e.g.*, benzodiazepines, sertraline)[14].the adaptogenic herb ashwagandha (*Withaniasomnifera*) reduced urinary tribulin in stressed animals[16]. The current four fields of adaptogen research are as follows: (a) phytochemistry: the separation and structural clarification of the active components of adaptogenic plants; (b) biochemistry and molecular biology: the mechanisms of adaptogens' stress-protective activity at the molecular and cellular levels; (c) clinical and experimental pharmacology: the effectiveness and safety of adaptogens in both human and animal stress-related disorders; and (d) pharmaceutical development of herbal preparations/products with proven medicinal uses in evidence-based medicine.[17]. The adaptogens affected many genes playing critical roles in the modulation of adaptive homeostasis, indicating their ability to modify gene expression to prevent stress-induced and aging-related disorders [18].Adaptogens reduce the intensity and negative impact of the stress caused by mental tension, emotional difficulties, poor lifestyle habits, disease and infection, pollution and other factors[19]. Prior research has shown how certain adaptogens affect important mediators of the stress response and pathways that modulate longevity. Overall, more than 70 plants have been described as adaptogenic [20].the cross-over of herbal concepts 'tonic' and 'adaptogen'

may represent the link between traditional use and modern terminology, and provide a foundation for further examination of the historical or traditional use of adaptogens[21]. The stressful human lifestyle of the 21st century has given rise to a wide variety of lifestyle diseases like hair loss, obesity, high blood pressure and fatigue. Chronic fatigue syndrome (CFS), also referred to as Royal Free disease [22]. Adaptogens are essentially prescribed for prophylactic purposes. However, they can also be used by healthy individuals to improve their cognitive and physical performance, in which case their efficacy is questionable[23].

2. Historical background:

2.1. Traditional uses of adaptogens:

From East Asian medicine to Western herbal medicine, many civilizations and regions of the world have long used herbal medications with adaptogenic properties in the context of adaptogenic activity. [24]. The emergence of a global formalisation of traditional medicine (TM) concepts via the World Health Organisation (WHO) highlights the importance of standardisation of TM concepts[21]. Historically, the notion adaptogens (phytoadaptogens) derived from an extensive survey and screening of active substances of botanical origin during 1960–1980 in USSR [3]. A team of researchers led by Hildebert Wagner, George Wikman, and Alexander Panossian conducted extensive research on adaptogens in the 1990s and put out the following definition: Adaptogens are naturally occurring bioregulators that improve the body's capacity to adjust to external conditions and prevent harm from them. [25]. The applications of these adaptogens have been known from the ancient times but the term adaptogens was introduced by a Russian scientist Lazarev in 1947 after an adaptogenic compound namely Dibazol (2-Benzylbenzimidazol) was discovered[26]. In mountain villages of Siberia, a bouquet of roots is still given to couples prior to marriage to enhance fertility and assure the birth of healthy children. In Middle Asia, R. rosea tea was the most effective treatment for cold and flu during severe Asian winters[27]. The Araliaceae family of plants, whose roots are frequently used as medicinal parts, are more prevalent in this list. The Korean ginseng [Panaxginseng] whose roots are used for various purposes, is the best known example of adaptogen plant[25]. Adaptogenic herbs include active plant elements known as phytochemicals. Examples of phytochemicals that contribute to our wellbeing are triterpenes, phenylpropanes, oxylipins and polysaccharides[28]. Ayurveda, the world's oldest medical system and a science of life, takes a holistic approach to health and

disease, emphasizing the preservation and promotion of good health as well as disease prevention through healthy lifestyle habits[29]. The most extensively researched are *Aralia mandschurica*, *Eleutherococcussenticosus*, *Rhodiolarosea* and *Schizandrachinensis*. Of these, *Rhodiolarosea* has the most pronounced effect on mental fatigue during stress and strain[30]. primarily in Russia and former USSR that preparations based on *Rhodiolarosea* rhizome and the glycoside salidroside (synonym: rhodioloside, rhodosine) have gained an established position and use within the official medicine. The use in medicine in the former USSR/Russia, goes back to a number of pharmacological and clinical investigations in the early 1960, which demonstrated primarily stimulant and anti-stress actions[31]. *R. rosea* has been used for centuries in the Republic of Georgia and Siberia to enhance fertility among the people living at high altitudes in the Caucasus Mountains[32]. Immunostimulating plant based studies showed that oral or intravenous administration of plant adaptogens proffers the prospect to reinstate immune competency during such immune allied alterations and immune compromised conditions[33]. *R. rosea* is a plant frequently used in traditional medicine in Eastern Europe and Asia for its "adaptogenic" qualities, meaning its ability to raise bodily resistance to physical, chemical, or biological stressors in experimental animals and people[34].

2.2. Development and Recognition in modern medicine:

Adaptogen as a new concept has become more generally recognized during the last 10 years and has recently been used as a functional term by health authorities (FDA, 1998)[35]. This phenomenon of adaptation to repetitive low-level stress was first described by Hans Selye in 1936 using rats exposed to low temperatures, low oxygen tension, muscular exercise, adrenaline, and morphine[36]. The term 'adaptogen' was first used formally and scientifically in the late 1940s, Russian toxicologist N. V. Lazarev coined the term "adaptogens" in 1947, initially referring to a synthetic compound (dibazol) that was found to enhance "non-specific resistance to stress." The idea of adaptogens as herbal substances that could boost the body's "non-specific resistance" to stress was formalized in Russia between 1950 and 1960[37]. Studies performed more recently, primarily in Germany and Japan, have shown a high level of consistency with the results of the Russian research[35]. Almost two decades later, the word 'adaptogen' was more explicitly defined when Brekhman and Dardymov (1969) proposed specified criteria that a chemical must meet to be classified as an adaptogen. [38]. Some adaptogenic plants have been

used in traditional Chinese medicine and Ayurveda for centuries to promote physical and mental health, improve the body's defense mechanisms, and enhance longevity[36]. A review article by Brekhman (1969), one of the pioneers in plant adaptogen research, summarized almost 20 years of Russian research and made Western scientists aware of the research and the concepts[39].

3.Mechanism of action :

3.1.Physiological effects :

Adaptogens serve to establish homeostasis, especially against stress, and stress alleviation is promoted by several sorts of mechanisms directly or indirectly by maintaining the levels of hormones such as cortisol, adrenaline, ACTH, and CRH [40]. Adaptogens act as challengers and mild stressors (stress-mimetics), giving rise to adaptive and stress-protective effects mainly associated with the HPA axis[41]. Adaptogens can increase the effectiveness of adrenal gland secretion, thereby abolishing excess hormone production[42]. The mode of action of corticosteroids is known to regulate carbohydrate, lipid, protein and nucleic acid metabolism, in order to mobilize the resources of the organism under stress to increase its resistance to damaging factors[43]. Stress activates the release of CRH from the hypothalamus, which in turn triggers the release of ACTH from the pituitary, leading to the secretion of adrenal hormones and NPY to mobilize energy and manage stress. To prevent an excessive response, cortisol is released from the adrenal cortex, where it binds to glucocorticoid receptors (GR) in the brain, initiating feedback regulation. [44]. Glutamate, acetylcholine, and serotonin postsynaptic receptors activate intracellular signaling pathways and transcription factors, leading to the expression of neuroprotective proteins such as antiapoptotic proteins, brain-mitochondrial uncoupling proteins (UCPs), and BDNF[45]. The stress system is thought to play a primary role in the body's responses to repeated stress and adaptation by balancing the releases of adrenaline (the 'switch-on' hormone), corticosteroids (the feedback regulatory 'switch-off' hormones that protect an organism from overreaction), and nitric oxide (which modulates the biosynthesis and effects of many hormones)[46].

3.2.Molecular And Cellular Mechanism :

laboratory work shows at least 88 of the 3516 genes identified as being regulated by adaptogens were closely associated with adaptive stress response and adaptive stress-response signalling

pathways (ASRSPs)[47]. Adaptogens stimulate cellular and organismal defense systems, activating intracellular and extracellular signaling pathways and expression of stress-activated proteins and neuropeptides, and enhancing survival against oxidative stress[48]. In general, herbal mixes achieve their bioactivities through synergistic interactions between individual components. This synergism can be attributed to the fact that medicinal herbs contain many different phytochemicals, which may mutually influence each other's activity[49]. Adaptogens' stress-protective action is associated with the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and the regulation of stress response mediators shared by all cells. Adaptogens function as low molecular weight "vaccines" or stress-mimetics, causing moderate activation of the stress system in order to cope with more severe stress[50]. Adaptogens have a diverse effects on cancer patients' health and well-being. First, they can modulate biological responses, modify immunological pathways, and thereby nonspecifically boost the human body's immunity. Second, adaptogens can promote bone marrow production, increase blood cell counts, and reduce infection[51]. Plant adaptogens enhance the neural system by mechanisms that are completely distinct from those of typical tonics. They are involved with metabolic regulation of several aspects of the stress system and modification of stimulus-response coupling[52]. selected adaptogenic extracts significantly attenuated FEC-induced regulation of more than 100 genes involved in the activation of neuronal death and inhibiting neurogenesis[53]. According to conventional wisdom it is reasonable to refer agents from actoprotectors' class to synthetic adaptogens and to regard their strong actoprotective effect as one of their components of adaptogenic action adaptogens of natural origin also can be referred to actoprotectors if they have potent influence on physical work capacity[54]. Adaptogens are natural plant growth regulators that help organisms adjust to changing conditions and avoid damage. adaptogens may have a direct impact on most facets of physical health and psychological state and, moreover, may indirectly improve aspects of social and environmental domains[55].

4.Common AadaptogenicPlants :

4.1.Rhodiolarosea :

Rhodiola rosea L. (Crassulaceae), commonly referred to as golden root or rose root, is a perennial herb that grows in high-altitude regions of the Arctic and mountainous areas across Europe and Asia. The roots of *R. rosea* have been traditionally used as a tonic and adaptogen in

Russia and as a hemostatic agent in Tibetan folk medicine. Various pharmacological effects of the roots of *R. rosea* have been reported, such as improvement of the memory and learning abilities, anti-stress and anticancer effects, etc [56].

4.1.1 Active compounds : Rhodiola rhizomes contains essential oils, fats, waxes, sterols, glycosides, organic acids (oxalic, citric, malic, gallic, succinic), phenolics including tannins and proteins[57]. A range of antioxidant compounds have been identified in Rhodiola rosea and acid), and flavonoids (catechins and proanthocyanidins)[58]. The rhizomes of *R. rosea*, we identified 10 components: salidroside, tyrosol, (+)-catechin, [epigallocatechin gallate](#), rosarin, rosavin, rosin, cinnamyl alcohol, rhodiosin, rhodionin[59]. Currently, more than 40 chemical compounds have been extracted from numerous Rhodiola plants. Among them, the main pharmacologically active ingredients are [salidroside](#) and its [aglycone tyrosol](#) [60]. The *Rhodiola rosea* extract named Rhodiola 5% is commercially available at Indena SpA (Milan, Italy) from the roots of *R. rosea* and standardized for 5% of rosavins, a class including rosarin (1), rosavin (2), and rosin (3), and for 1.8% of salidroside (4) [61].

4.1.2 Clinical evidence and application : *Rhodiola rosea* L. (Crassulaceae) is an [adaptogen](#) plant also known as arctic root, It is traditionally used in Eastern Europe and Asia to stimulate the nervous system[62]. Rhodiola Rosea extracts (RRE) stimulate the brain and increase the concentration level of [neurotransmitters](#) such as [norepinephrine](#) (NE), serotonin (5 H T) [acetylcholine](#) (Ach), and Dopamine (DA),⁶⁷ At the cortical and [brainstem](#) level it was demonstrated that sub-chronic treatment (10 days) with RRE increased the concentration of serotonin[63]. *Rhodiola rosea* is used as stimulant for the central nervous system (CNS), to enhance work performance, longevity and resistance to high altitude sickness, and to restore from fatigue and to care symptoms of asthenia subsequent to intense physical and psychological stress[64] Rhodiola rosea appears to relieve many of the neuropsychological symptoms reported by menopausal women, including fatigue, anxiety, depression, cognitive dysfunction, memory deterioration, impaired executive functioning, and stress intolerance[65]. Rhodiola rosea is a medicinal plant with numerous health advantages, including exhaustion, anti-inflammatory, anti-neoplastic, antihepatotoxic, and nerve-protective properties. It has been employed as a functional agent in Asian folkloric medicines, particularly traditional Chinese medicine, since ancient times [66] Polysaccharide is one of the key active components with antioxidant, immunological

modulation, anti-inflammatory, and anti-diabetic properties.. Furthermore, many researchers have shown that natural polysaccharides have an inhibitory effect on the proliferation of various tumor cells[67]. *R. rosea* prevents exercise-induced ATP decrease in mitochondria after exhaustive swimming[68]. *R. rosea* extracts have been reported to reduce also behavioral responses evoked by central CRF administration, such as CRF-induced anorexia *R. rosea* extract influence the expression molecular chaperones particularly Hsp70 is up-regulated by *R. rosea* extracts and is responsible for inhibition of NO synthase II gene and interaction with glucocorticoid receptors[69]. *R. rosea* ingestion can improve cognitive function, reduce mental fatigue, promote free radical mitigation, and has anti-oxidative effect and neuroprotective effect, and increase endurance performance, and learning and memory[70]. The adaptogenic efficacy of RR in minimizing muscle injury during heavy exercise for athletes remains appealing. For example, report RR supplementation decreased exercise-induced inflammation and muscle damage during a 6-day period of intensified exercise in untrained subjects[71]. Modern pharmacological studies showed that *Rhodiola* has many functions such as anti-anxiety , anti-aging , anti-depressant , immune regulation , and hepatoprotection. Salidroside is nontoxic and harmless to the human body and conforms to the life philosophy of modern people, which is applied to daily chemical products such as cosmetics and detergents[72]. *Rhodiola* spp. have been developed into skincare products that exhibit effects such as delaying skin aging, moisturizing, and enhancing complexion, reducing dullness and yellowness[73]. the oligomeric proanthocyanidins from root of *Rhodiola rosea* (OPCRR) exhibited significant free radical-scavenging activities, antioxidant activities *in vivo* and lipid lowering effects[74].

4.2.Ashwagandha(withaniasomnifera):

Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) commonly referred to as "Indian Ginseng" or "Winter Cherry," is a member of the Solanaceae family [75]. It is one such essential medicinal plant and has been used as an Ayurvedic rasayana since ancient culture[76]. Ashwagandha is a herb natively originated in Asia, particularly India, and found in the Middle East and parts of Africa [77].

4.2.1 Active compounds : The chemical composition of ashwagandha has been extensively studied and found several groups of bioactive chemical constituents such as flavonoids, tannin, alkaloids, sitoindosides, glycosides, withanicil[78]. the phytochemical constituents such as

alkaloids, steroidal lactones, saponins, glycol-withanolides present in it [79]. Several withanolides, including withaferin A, withanolide A, withanoside IV, sitoindosides, and alkaloids, have been discovered and segregated from WS. These compounds are mainly localized in mature leaves and roots[80]. phytoconstituents of *Ashwagandha* are , withanoside I-VII, withasilolide A-F, glucosomniferanolide, withasomnilide, withasomniferanolide, withanamide A-I, somniferanolide, somniferawithanolide, somniwithanolide, somniferine, pseudo-withanine[81]. Withanolides such as Withanone (WN), Withanolide-D, and so on are naturally occurring C28 steroids, built on an ergostane skeleton functionalized at carbons 1, 22, and 26[82].

4.2.2 Clinical evidence and applications : Ashwagandha (ASH) has been used for treatment of various neurological disorders like memory and cognitive function (Medhya), anxiety (chinta), Parkinson's disease (Kampavatha), sleep disorders (Nidranasa) etc.[83] A broad spectrum of pharmacological activities, occurring at different concentrations (μg to mg), includes promoting apoptosis, inducing cytotoxicity, inhibiting cell division, and exhibiting anti-metastatic and anti-angiogenic effects. Notably, they display anti-proliferative activity against cancer cell lines associated with colon, lung, breast, pancreatic, and prostate cancers[84]. Extracts of Ashwagandha are utilized for remedies against inflammation, arthritis, diabetes, stress, asthma, and hypertension [85]. In Indian medicine, ASH is considered one of the main herbal components of geriatric tonics, and is regarded as aphrodisiac, narcotic, diuretic, anthelmintic, astringent, thermogenic, and stimulant[86]. WS root extract enhances cognitive processes and augments mental recall capacity following diabetes, amyloid β , scopolamine and foot shock stress related memory loss[87]. Ashwagandha, including its ability to cure hiccups and feminine problems. The ethnomedicinal usage of this plant indicated as per 'Ayurveda' texts as kṣaya (~pthisis), daurbalya (~weakness), vātaroga (disorders of vāta), śoṭha (~swelling), and klaibya (~impotency)[88]. Pre-clinical and clinical investigations have shown that Ashwagandha roots and extracts have adaptogenic, immunomodulatory, anxiolytic, anti-stress, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, anti-aging, cardioprotective, sleep disturbance, hypothyroidism, and other properties [89]. Ashwagandha can regulate the processes of metabolism, foster homeostasis, and revitalize the body as an adaptogen.[90]. *Ashwagandha ghrita* (AG) is an

effective *ghrita* formulation beneficial for treatment of weakness, gynaecological disorders, general debility and infertility[91].

4.3.ginseng [panax ginseng]

Ginseng, a shade-requiring perennial herb with fleshy roots and green oval-shaped leaves, refers to several plant species in the *Panax* genus[92]. the *Panax* genus in the Araliaceae family, has been a staple in East Asian traditional medicine for thousands of years [93]. The ginseng root is the main part of ginseng used in medicine[94]. This remarkable herb has earned the title "king of herbs" and holds significant value as a traditional herbal medicine and essential raw material for healthcare products in China [95].

4.3.1Active compound : *ginseng's* various effects are exerted by multiple ingredients, making it challenging to identify active compounds and their key mechanisms[96]. Main components of *P. ginseng* are saponins, which include protopanaxadiol (PPD)- and protopanaxatriol (PPT)-type ginsenosides[97]. The ginsenosides have been characterized or isolated from the roots and rhizomes of *Panax ginseng* are helpful for us to characterize the selected ligands[98]. The percentage of various ginsenosides in ginseng total saponins were as follows: ginsenoside Ra (2.91%), ginsenoside Rb1 (18.26%), ginsenoside Rb2 (9.07%), ginsenoside Rc (9.65%), ginsenoside Rd (8.24%), ginsenoside Re (9.28%), ginsenoside Rf (3.48%), ginsenoside Rg1 (6.42%), ginsenoside Rg2 (3.63%), ginsenoside Rg3 (4.70%), ginsenoside Ro (3.82%), and other minor components.[99].

4.3.2clinical evidence and applications : Ginseng may provide anti-aging and life-extending benefits. Current pharmacological investigations have confirmed the anti-ageing properties of ginseng via processes including scavenging oxygen free radicals and controlling endocrine function and immunity[100]. the root of *Panax ginseng* has been traditionally used for the treatment of central nervous system diseases, such as learning and memory deficits, mood disorders, etc .[101]. . Ginseng is renowned for its various functions, including enhancing vitality, strengthening pulse, invigorating the spleen, and benefiting the lungs, thereby promoting body fluids, nourishing blood, soothing nerves, and enhancing wisdom[102]. *Panax ginseng* C.A. Mey (PG), a traditional Chinese medicine, has been used for thousands of years. PG generates a "Qi-invigorating" action, which serves to avoid oxidative stress and optimize energy

metabolism.[103]. Ginseng flowers have a different of therapeutic effects, involving anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immune system modulator, and antineoplastic activity. Ginsenosides have been demonstrated thus far to be potential therapeutic agents for the management of a variety of inflammatory illnesses and have been crucial in the treatment of liver problems[104]. clinical and animal studies supports the therapeutic potential of ginseng in relieving fatigue[105]. Panax ginseng has been widely used around the world as both a medicinal treatment and a dietary supplement for various health issues. It is highly regarded in Eastern medicine for enhancing overall health, boosting vitality, and promoting longevity. Additionally, P. ginseng has a therapeutic effect on and is an attractive alternative for patients with insomnia, some of whom are reluctant to use traditional medications[106].

4.4.Holy basil :

Holy basil, also known as tulsi (*Ocimum tenuiflorum* L., synonym *O. sanctum* L.; family Lamiaceae), is an aromatic perennial herb with sacred applications in Hinduism and several defensive and medicinal properties in Ayurveda. It is widely distributed and cultivated in Tropical Asia. Various forms of holy basil were found. They are usually noticeable by leaf size, leaf color, aroma, and pubescence.[107]. *Ocimum Sanctum* (OS) often known as Holy Basil or Tulsi, has contributed essential value to herbal treatments[108]. For thousands of years, it has been used in Ayurvedic and Siddha therapy to treat infections, skin and liver disorders, and prevent snake and scorpion bites. The leaves of *O. sanctum* are the source of an essential oil which has numerous medicinal properties.[109].

4.4.1Active compounds : Basil oil is rich in valuable bioactive compounds, consisting of a diverse blend of phenylpropanoid and terpenoid derivatives. Two key compounds found in basil oil are methyl eugenol and β -caryophyllene[110]. The plant leaves include nutrients like protein, vitamins, and minerals. Basil leaves have also been claimed to be high in vitamins B and C. Basil is also rich in some valuable phytochemicals such as terpenoids, essential oils, phenols, flavonoids, and anthocyanins[111].

4.4.2Clinical evidence and applications : The plant's medicinal and curative capabilities are complemented by its culinary usage as a flavorant and aromatic, increasing its commercial worth. The rich essential oils extend modern applications that include religious, therapeutic,

gastronomic, nutritional, aromatic, and ornamental uses (Tangpao et al., 2018). Moreover, essential oils from Holy basil have insecticidal, mosquito repellent, and antileishmanial properties and are widely used as food additives and perfumes[112]. Holy basil leaves (*Ocimum tenuiflorum* L) are well-known herbs available throughout Malaysia including neighbouring countries and they are commonly used for the treatment of various diseases including diabetes mellitus[113]. Holy basil (*Ocimum sanctum*) is known as tulsi and is reported to have antibactericidal and insecticidal properties[114]. The plant has been shown to be useful against respiratory syndrome, colds, fevers, indigestion, diarrhea, headaches, bronchitis, coughs, hysteria, and many other conditions. Eugenol is an active ingredient found mostly in the herb's leaves and inflorescence, which contributes to its therapeutic potential as a pain reliever and decreases blood glucose levels in type 2 diabetics. Sacred basil has remained largely as a household species in India for many years[115]. *Ocimum gratissimum* is a fragrant, upright, hairy herb commonly used to relieve nasal congestion, make flavorful teas, repel mosquitoes, and treat snake bites. A review of existing literature has shown that *O. gratissimum* possesses antimicrobial properties against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, antifungal effects against *Alternaria alternata* and *Alternaria tenuissima*, as well as insecticidal and repellent actions against various insect species. Several studies have shown a repellent effect on pests when the crop was intercropped with *Ocimum* species[116]. *O. sanctum* was originally described as a medicinal plant in ancient Ayurvedic literature such as Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, and Rigveda (3500-1600 BCE), and it was traditionally used to cure poisoning, impotence, and arthritis. Currently, it is mostly utilized as a nerve tonic, as *O. sanctum* has the ability to adapt an organism to stress and hence is classed as a major adaptogen. The therapeutic potential of *O. sanctum* is much broader, and it is currently being studied for its anti-cancer, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, radiation protective, anti-microbial and anti-stress properties[117].

5. Clinical applications :

5.1. stress related disorders:

1. Anxiety and Stress Relief: Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng have been shown to reduce anxiety and stress levels.

2. Depression: Adaptogens like St. John's Wort, S-adenosylmethionine (SAME), and omega-3 fatty acids have been used to treat depression.

3. Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD): Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng may help improve focus and attention in individuals with ADHD.

5.2.Physical health :

1. Fatigue and Energy: Adaptogens like ginseng, ashwagandha, and rhodiola can help increase energy levels and reduce fatigue.

2. Sleep Disorders: Adaptogens like valerian root, melatonin, and ashwagandha can help regulate sleep patterns and improve sleep quality.

3. Exercise Performance and Recovery: Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng may help improve exercise performance, reduce muscle damage, and enhance recovery.

5.3.Cognitive function and performance :

1. Neuroprotection: Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng may help protect against neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's.

2. Cognitive Function: Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng may help improve cognitive function, including attention, memory, and executive function.

5.4.Immune system and inflammation

1. Immune System Support: Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng may help support immune function and reduce inflammation.

2. Anti-Inflammatory Effects: Adaptogens like turmeric, ginger, and ashwagandha have anti-inflammatory properties, which may help reduce inflammation and improve symptoms in conditions like arthritis.

5.5.Other clinical applications

1. Cardiovascular Health: Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng may help reduce blood pressure, improve lipid profiles, and prevent cardiovascular disease.

2. Gastrointestinal Health: Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng may help reduce stress-related gastrointestinal symptoms and improve gut health.

3. Menopausal Symptoms: Adaptogens like ashwagandha, rhodiola, and ginseng may help reduce menopausal symptoms like hot flashes, night sweats, and mood changes.

6.Discussion :

Adaptogens represent an interesting group of plants, which in the last few years have been receiving attention both by scientists and by consumers in general, particularly as part of contemporary stress management and health. Adaptogens are understood to possess a unique property—the ability to facilitate the body to adapt to stress, enhance resistance, and enhance homeostasis. They simply modulate the body's stress response, making it less injurious to health and wellbeing. Some of the most popular adaptogens include Ashwagandha, Rhodiola Rosea, Holy Basil, also known as Tulsi, and Ginseng. They have long been used traditionally in systems like Ayurvedic medicine and Traditional Chinese Medicine but are now being brought back into pharmacy and re-examined for potential benefits in treating chronic stress, fatigue, anxiety, and even depression. Adaptogens are thought to act by modulating the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, which is an important part of the body's stress response. They help to balance the body's stress system by modulating cortisol levels, the stress hormone, and thereby enhance stress resilience. They may also have antioxidant properties, support cellular repair, and improve energy metabolism, all of which can contribute to overall wellbeing under stress. Adaptogens represent very interesting topics to be considered in modern pharmacy, offering potential alternatives or adjuncts to conventional treatments against stress and its related symptoms. However, they should be regarded with balanced reasoning by science as a whole, and end consumers within society, with promise on one hand while further research is needed on the other regarding their efficacy and safety.

7.CONCLUSION :

Natural plant adaptogens are promising substances with broad effects that help alleviate stress, illness, physical weakness, anxiety, and enhance mental well-being. While the use of these adaptogens dates back to ancient times, their popularity is growing in modern society due to their healing and stress-resistance properties. These plant-based products can be consumed in the form of tea, food, or as medicine and supplements. Adaptogens represent a fascinating intersection between traditional herbal medicine and modern pharmacotherapy. As research continues to unveil their potential benefits, these plants may play an increasingly significant role in managing stress-related conditions within contemporary healthcare frameworks. The beneficial stress-protective effects of adaptogens have been shown to be linked to the regulation of homeostasis through various mechanisms, including involvement with the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and the modulation of key mediators of the stress response, such as molecular chaperones. While adaptogens vary subtly in their effects, we do not claim to have definitive answers regarding the best uses for each one.

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